

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

UNIVERSITY OF BARCELONA

Master of Science Thesis

Exploring Plasticity Rules in the Biologically Realistic Simulation of Neuronal Cultures

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Plastizitätsregeln in biologisch realistischer Simulation von neuronalen Zellkulturen

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I confirm that this master of science thesis is my own work and I have documented all sources and material used.

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Abstract

Neuronal cell cultures have served as a pivotal platform for neuroscience experiments since the early 20th century. However, despite their long history of use, the processes governing the development of connectivity and firing patterns in these cultures remain inadequately understood. In this master's thesis, I endeavor to bridge this knowledge gap by integrating straightforward plasticity rules with established models of neuronal culture growth and activity. The objective is to create a comprehensive and realistic simulation of neuronal culture development, which can be effectively employed as a digital twin of real-world neuronal culture experiments. To demonstrate the utility of this simulation, I present a case study involving the silencing of neuronal activity using CNQX as an example. This innovative approach promises to advance our understanding of neuronal culture dynamics, providing valuable insights into the behavior of neuronal cell cultures. By offering a powerful digital tool for experimentation and analysis, this work contributes to the ongoing exploration of neuroscience and opens up new avenues for research and discovery.

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1 Introduction

"In our enthusiasm for the novelty of the method we may forget the fundamental problems to the solution of which it may be able to contribute - if used critically" - Ross G Harrison [1]

Biology made a huge leap during the 19th, 20th and 21st centuries to allow for unprecedented level of detailed insight and manipulation of living matter. Neurobiology is a field of biology investigating nervous systems and their interaction with the rest of the matter involved in organisms. It consists of many subdisciplines. Notable researchers in the field - be it Pavlov with reflexes, Ramon y Cajal with morphology of neurons or Hans Berger with EEG waves - approached the topic of Neurobiology from different perspectives and vastly different sets of experiments. But somewhere, they all still worked under the same "hood" with arguably the same aim - to investigate the nervous system and the way it works.

One of the most interesting questions that probably have troubled humanity since its conception we could rephrase as following - what is a human's soul, and where is it located? Even with current unprecedented progress in Neuroscience, little can be said for sure on this matter. It is interesting to note the artistic contribution to the development of Neuroscience: gradually, with coming of Renaissance the searchlight for soul has gradually been shifting from heart and other parts of body to the brain. Is there a reason behind that? Arguably, this is the tremendous complexity of the brain that has been discovered by biologists and doctors, the complexity that has fascinated Nissl, Cajal and their contemporary colleagues and continues to fascinate us in the 21st century. Arguably, our society slowly but steadily gets more and more based in "rationality" and "intelligence" as it transits to "knowledge-based society". Fields like Artificial Intelligence are a common trend now. And there is no place to observe the build-up of biological mechanisms for intelligence as the brain. In light of this, among other things, the "Brain Decade" has been declared in the U. S. already more than 20 years ago. Since then, there has been a considerable progress on understanding the brain, nervous system and its function - but still there is very much to discover.

How to "crack the code" of the brain and the nervous system? This sounds like a very mechanistic and precisely formulated goal: yet, organisms are not so stable and defined in time - they proliferate and move (and so do the organisms cells!), possess a considerable variability and struggle to pertain their "default state" [2]. While brain might seem less reliable than computer, there are many upsides to the "brain computation" - organic materials makeup, less carbon emissions and energy consumption at the same estimated efficiency. Brains also normally take up less space and provide increased flexibility and adjustability to the environment.

iPSC technology with the Nobel Prize in 2008 revolutionized neuronal cell culturing. CRISPR/-Cas9 technology allows to modify the genome of a cell at a specified place and/or alter other

Figure 1.1: Neurorecording methods types. **A** Electrical recordings usually use columnar metallic arrays to capture signals. **B** Optical recordings use light to illuminate and capture photons from neuronal imaging agents. **C** Magnetic resonance methods use magnetic properties of EM waves. **D** Molecular recording techniques are based on chemical/molecular specificity of recording agents. Source: [3].

cellular processes like gene expression. Furthermore, in the recent years there has been an increasing interest to "organoids" - small organ-like tissue patches that serve as a model for different organs in living species, or viewed as phenomena on their own. Molecular biological, optical and electrical neuro-recording techniques have been dramatically improved recently, which allows to apply them to neuronal cell cultures in a high-throughput fashion. Nowadays, there are many types of neuro-recording methods available, ranging in their space and time precision and invasivity (Figure 1.1).

During the last few decades, enormous improvements also have been made for high-throughput and large scale neural recordings.

Altogether, this gives us a possibility of studying **neuronal cell cultures** instead of studying the animal brain. One would remove a cell from an organism without a severe organism damage, knock it "back" to the undifferentiated stem cell state and then "reprogram" this stem

cell to be a neuron. With many technicalities that need to be taken care of like inducing a specific cell type, proliferation sequence, the precision of experimental protocol and control for confounders, in principle this approach works more or less reliably now and provides a platform for new insights.

With state-of-the-art neuronal culture methods, we can approach the question of neural information processing *constructing* a neural processing device *in vitro* rather than analyzing animal "devices" *in vivo*. Apart from this, the superior recording and stimulation precision of chemical, electrophysiological and optical signals might be available *in vitro* rather than *in vivo*. *in vitro* research also does not harm and nivellate any animal.

First large-scale experiments on brain tissue signalling *in vitro* date around 20 years back. The field of neuronal cell culture recordings has undergone significant developments since then. Organoids and neuronal cultures are becoming increasingly popular in high-throughput clinical research and drug testing. The betterment of neurobiological models and the appearance of a new Frontier journal recently termed Organoid Intelligence allow scientists across the world to create more plausible models of brain in a dish and collaborate as a community. With the besaid developments in neuro-recording methods and molecular biological methods applied to neuronal cell cultures, cheaper, preciser and more scalable biological investigation of neuronal cultures is also made possible. Further developments like perfusion of brain organoids with blood vessels, as well as preciser and faster imaging methods [4] are currently being developed.

1.1 Limitations of experimental data

Most commonly used neuro-recording methods for the type of experiments my simulation accounts for are MEAs (with or without stimulation electrodes) and Calcium imaging. Both of these recording modalities are subject to different types of noise. First, there is biological noise due to the spontaneous changes in neuron's environment and/or internal stage. It is usually taken care of by the neuronal activity models. Another type of noise is the inherent noise of the recording modality, that is photon noise in Calcium imaging [5], as well as thermal noise and ADC precision loss in MEA recordings [6]. Another factor is the impact of the imaging modality on the biological state of neurons: for instance calcium imaging procedures can abnormally deplete neuronal cultures of calcium, which impacts their lifecycle [7]. Calcium imaging is prone to bleaching over time. Sometimes, it is also not possible to penetrate to single-neuron precision with Calcium imaging, which makes it necessary to subsume several physically adjacent neurons as one *Region of Interest (ROI)*. This problem is also present with MEA modality. Above all it is important to remember that Calcium imaging is merely a proxy measurement for the "underlying" neuronal activity, as it measures Calcium influx and efflux of the neuron and not the Action Potentials directly. Apart from this, Calcium fluorescence operates on a much longer timescale than Calcium influx and efflux due to a longer fluorescence decay and can reach *fraction of seconds* order as compared to *microseconds* during which Action Potentials and calcium concentrations change. This can of course bring many issues to the "spike distinguishability" of the method, however there are

improving algorithmic and biochemical methods to account for the inherent problems with physical realities of Calcium imaging [8] [9]. Major limitations of MEA recordings include low Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) due to high impedance of the electrode/solution interface, as well as the trade-off between electrode size and recording noise level and charge induction capabilities [6]. It is imperative to carefully measure and control for the input charge to neurons during stimulation, because there is a range of current neurons can handle above which their biological and firing properties can be impaired. In the worst case scenario not careful electrical stimulation of neurons in the culture can lead to neuronal death.

Another important experimental factor is that the plate is not a natural milieu for neurons. Compared to the biophysical realities of the brain, things are vastly different in the "dish": there is a different neuronal density, different compartmentalization. Currently, best efforts are given to grow a biologically realistic network and neuronal composition *in vitro*. Main axes are: excitatory/inhibitory neurons balance, neuronal density, growth of microglia and astrocytes in the dish, perfusion of cultures with blood vessels (extremely important for 3D cell cultures), neuronal maturation and plausible neuronal geometry [10] [11]. It is also becoming increasingly possible to differentiate for neurons of a specific receptor type [12] as well as control for neuronal fate, but the issue is of course the fine-tuning of such control and application to a neuron in context of a culture.

This inconsistency of the reality of the culture in a dish as compared to a healthy brain in the context of an organism becomes acute with drastic changes to cell milieu, most prominent of which is *addition of chemical factors to the colony*. This is usually done with either purpose of drug screening [13] or perturbation of the culture's firing activity. Especially in the latter case neurons can undergo strong and detrimental biological and structural changes if the new firing pattern is vastly different from the usual one (in terms of firing rate/metabolites release). For example, CNQX-mediated silencing of excitatory neurons in the colony for several days represents a pathological state for these neurons, which can have a lasting impact on their life cycle and activity even after CNQX is completely washed off. Another important aspect is how mature the neurons and the culture as a whole are. It has been proven that mature brains function differently than their younger counterparts [14].

It is important to keep in mind that many of these phenomena are not being accounted for by the current model, which solely focuses on neuronal firing patterns and tries to model changes in neuronal state using some very simplified models to account for efficiency and interpretability.

1.2 Important neuronal culture phenomena

The easiest way to dissect neuronal cultures activity analytically is to model its building bricks over time. There are 2 principal components to it: neuronal and synaptic activity.

1.2.1 Neuronal activity

Living organism's neuronal system is comprised of neurons and other cells. Oligodendrocytes, microglia and astrocytes, traditionally viewed as "support" cells, play an important role in immune response, protection, nutrition and help in signal transduction of the nervous system. It is an active area of research: a recent discovery shows that microglia also play regulatory part in neuronal activity [15]. Still, the traditional approach views neurons as the only cells that are able to transduce spikes of membrane depolarization called Action Potentials. Its origins discovered by Luigi Galvani and first full recording of an Action Potential performed by Julius Bernstein in the XIX century, it has been long hypothesized to be an atomic unit of information in the brain [16].

Atomic signal unit hypothesis allows to describe signaling processes in neural tissue with rather trivial mathematical models. There are dozens of different models for this, highlighting different dynamics as principal [17]. On a higher level, one could chose between precise signal times or signal rates as a principal information conveying unit [18]. An exact decision about the choice of the model of neuron activity depends on many things: which aspect of neuron population's activity we are most interested in? How much efficiency are we ready to sacrifice for a more detailed model of what happens? These are examples of the questions one would ask before choosing a specific model.

1.2.2 Synaptic plasticity

Synapses connect neurons. To view them as stationary "junctions" remaining static throughout a neuronal population's lifetime is possible, yet such a perspective is often too imprecise. Synapses are a dynamic construct, having the ability to grow, shrink, connect and disconnect from other neurons. This is termed *synaptic plasticity* and is a very important aspect of neuronal population activity. A common hypothesis is that it plays an important role in various functions of neural circuits like learning and memory [19]. Again, *synaptic plasticity* is an umbrella term for a variety of dynamic processes happening to synapses. Different mechanisms of synaptic plasticity possess different dynamics with different biological reasoning [17]. One should proceed with care about the choice of an exact model.

1.3 Experiments on 2D neuronal cell cultures

Alongside with studying the nervous systems of animals and within them, one of the fascinating methods of Neuroscience research is to study nervous cells outside of animal body. This method of studying neuronal growth and anatomical properties has been employed since Cajal times [20].

Studying cultured neurons has been a breakthrough around 1910. However, it really took off during two decades after 1980s [21]. In the referred article, authors argue that the increased utility of neuronal cultures has come from many factors, perhaps most importantly environmental factors understanding in neural development, as well as biochemical modulation. It has been possible to stain for neuronal processes selectively, as well as study biophysical

properties down to the precision of a single receptor using e.g. patch clamp techniques (ibid.). The authors of the article were looking forward to the modern developments of the field when they underlined the importance of image processing as well as genetic modifications for the development of the field. They also foretold the extended use of primary cell cultures - and it would not be for another 10 years that induced pluripotent stem cells would revolutionize the field even further on this axis [22]. Current high-throughput high-precision neuronal growth and recording techniques allow to record and manipulate culture's activity down to a single-neuron precision.

There are few things known about *in vitro* neuronal culture behavior. For instance, normal 2D cultures are strongly bursting with a propagating wavefront and limited "nucleation sites", i.e. the sites of burst onset. There are different hypotheses as to what is the reason and the purpose of the nucleation sites, one of which is noise focusing [23].

Bursts in cultures is arguably one of the most interesting phenomena in their activity. Burst onset sites, globality and propagation velocity are some of the burst metrics that can be studied. In different environments and on different stages, cultures can have different burst activity.

Topological patterning with PDMS and Neuro-engineering methods serves increased functionalization and modularization, generating a richer activity repertoire of the culture [24] [25]. Increased modularity of the culture makes it more resemblant of *in vivo* neural tissue and allows for generation of more various activity patterns.

1.4 Aim of the thesis

The aim of my thesis was to combine a plausible network growth model of the neuronal culture based on geometrically plausible connections between neurons [23], a plausible and efficient neuronal activity model [26] with synaptic plasticity mechanisms to simulate development of neuronal culture connectivity and activity in spontaneous or stimulated milieu. I hoped to be able to better understand the underpinning principles driving culture's development and to save experimental costs by interrogating this digital twin of the culture.

2 In-silico simulation of 2D neuronal culture activity

The main deliverable of my research work is presented in this chapter. I have devised a biologically plausible model of changing connectivity inside the 2D neuronal culture as the culture develops.

2.1 Theoretical basis of the culture connectivity

To simulate connectivity changes in a neuronal culture, it is first inevitable to make some assumptions to what this connectivity signifies to the culture function and what are the drivers for its change. The theoretical framework for that is depicted in Figure 2.1. Firing influences structure according to a coupling function f . This function depends on $c(s, t)$ - pairwise connectivity changes between series of neurons s (source) and t (target). Furthermore, it depends on homeostasis functions $h(s, t, N)$ which can take pairwise neurons into account like $c(s, t)$, but also sometimes the whole network state N . Structural changes influence firing back: using a coupling function st which only takes into account pairs of neurons. Due to measurement noise, as well as estimation noise, we can only get approximations on firing and structural coupling between neurons.

It is the basis for all investigation of 2D neuronal cell cultures activity that such a culture exhibits firing in form of Action Potentials. What I have first hypothesized on, is that is due to this firing that the colony changes its structural connectivity. Put more precisely: taken two neurons s and t in the culture and their firing histories $s_f^{1..t}$ and $t_f^{1..t}$, one can know how the structural connectivity, i.e. physical connections between these two neurons change. Later on, I have adjusted this hypothesis to leave out the *structural* connectivity because of the lack of ground truth and even noisy experimental data about structural connectivity in the culture. The updated hypothesis sounds as following: there is a coupling between prior firing activity of neurons and their future activity which can be simulated in terms of biologically plausible mathematical functions. In context of this work, I refer to these functions as *plasticity functions* and *plasticity mechanisms*. I still hypothesize that some background structural changes in physical connections between neurons happen, but I do not concern with these changes in the context of this work. They are hidden - and here it is enough to know that whatever these changes are and whichever form they take, they drive the change in firing activity of the culture which is indeed visible and can be analysed. Expressed as a diagram, there is indeed a coupling between the culture's spikes to the culture's physical connectivity between neurons. Then there is also a coupling back from structural to "functional" neuronal connectivity, i.e. that the structural changes induce firing changes in the culture. In the context of this work,

Figure 2.1: Overview of structural and functional modalities in a neuronal network. f - firing coupling function, $c(s, t)$ - pairwise connectivity changes, s source, t target. $h(s, t, N)$ homeostasis function, $c(s, t)$ connectivity change, N network state. st structural changes influence. See 2 for more details.

both of these couplings are subsumed as one collective *connectivity change* phenomenon, which is being constructed in the simulation and validated in comparison to the observations from the experiments.

2.2 Culture geometry modelling

The simulation begins with laying out a plausible geometry for the modelled culture. This includes positioning neurons and wiring them to each other. An example of a network is shown in Figure 2.2.

The approach I have employed is depicted on Figure 2.3 and described in detail in [23]. In rough terms, simulation creates a random network which is concordant with a specified excitatory and inhibitory neurons amount (which are also distributed randomly around the surface) as well as neuronal density. It then starts to grow axons from neurons segment-for-segment. The angle of each segments deviates with an angle drawn from a Gaussian white noise distribution from the angle of the previous segment. The length of each axon is drawn from a Rayleigh distribution

I define the weights of the resulting adjacency matrix using a uniform distribution in the range $[0, MAX_EXCITATORY_WEIGHT]$ for excitatory neurons' outgoing connections, and $[-MAX_INHIBITORY_WEIGHT, 0]$ for inhibitory neurons' outgoing connections. Both weight boundaries are specified in the simulation based on experience. This way, a starting (sparsely) geometrically plausible model of neuronal culture connectivity is attained.

Figure 2.2: An example of the network produced by the described algorithm. Blue dots are neuronal somas (size not up to scale); black lines are connections between neurons. Direction and connection strength are not shown for better visibility.

Figure 2.3: Metric construction of the neuronal network. For clarity only 4 neurons are shown. Somas are depicted by circles with solid borders. Axons are indicated by grey curved lines. Once an axon crosses the active dendritic tree area of another neuron (colour filled circles with dashed borders), a directed connection (solid black arrow) is established with a certain probability. Source: [23]

Figure 2.4: FitzHugh-Nagumo dynamics. Right panel shows magnified and simplified view, out of which the so-called Izhikevich model is derived.

2.3 Simulation core functionality

2.3.1 Single neuronal activity modelling

To model neuronal activity, I have employed the so-called Izhikevich neuronal model [26]. This model of neurons is a simplification of FitzHugh Nagumo dynamics (Figure 2.4).

One of its dynamical equations is quadratic, which makes this model nonlinear. The dynamics of this model are governed by two variables, u and v . v is arguably the main variable, interpreted as a collective *transmembrane potential* of a given neuron soma. u is an "artificially constructed" recovery variable and does not have 1 to 1 biological correspondence. The equations of this model are:

$$\begin{aligned} v' &= 0.04v^2 + 5v + 140 - u + I \\ u' &= a(bv - u) \end{aligned}$$

I signifies the external input current to the neuron, a and b are neuron type-specific parameter variables. After a neuron reaches the transmembrane potential (v) of $30mV$, its potential is being reset to c , and its (normally decaying) recovery variable is being increased by d . c and d are also neuron-type specific.

The original paper of Izhikevich suggests different models with different behaviours based on a , b , c and d values which have been fitted to the real neuronal activity data of the neocortex across mammalian species and experiments.

In my simulation, I have used the so-called Regular Spiking neurons to model all excitatory neurons and Fast Spiking neurons to model all inhibitory neurons, a simplification approach proposed by Izhikevich himself (ibid.).

I parameter is used to model either targeted stimulation of neurons or spontaneous activity fluctuations (either due to neuron intrinsic state or environmental influence). I have

Figure 2.5: Time interval between pre- and post-synaptic spikes affects synaptic weight change in Spike time-dependent plasticity (STDP). This goes in both directions (pre- to post-spike and post- to pre-spike). Lines depict an analytical smooth function fitted to observations depicted by dots. Source: [17]

modeled spontaneous activity fluctuations as $U(0, NOISE_MAX)$ for excitatory neurons ($NOISE_MAX = 5$ by default) and $U(0, 2)$ for inhibitory neurons (U is uniform distribution; see Glossary).

2.3.2 Platicity rules

Spike-dependent time plasticity

The besaid coupling between firing activity and connectivity changes was modelled using a pleiad of *plasticity rules*. First, a spike time-dependent plasticity rule was employed to account for the rewiring of synaptic connections [27] (Figure 2.5). Governed by the Hebbian principle of "what fires together, wires together", I have employed an efficient approach to STDP advised to me by my colleague Akke Mats Houben, and equivalent to the one showed in Figure 2.5. Each neuron has a dynamic STDP plasticity vector A attached to it. All A s are initiated to 0 at the beginning of the simulation. For each time a neuron i fires, the value of A_i is updated by the value β_{Hebb} ($\Delta A_i = \beta_{Hebb}$). Denote W_{ij} the directed connection weight of j to i , and W_{ji} the directed connection weight of i to j . Then, the connectivity weight W_{ij} for each neuron j is increased by A_j (hereby, we count the previous spike of neuron j is the pre-synaptic spike). W_{ji} is being decreased by the same value (A_j). This signifies directional rewiring of connection weights once a pre-synaptic spike of neuron j is followed

by a post-synaptic spike of neuron i .

In the NEST simulations, I have used a different version of STDP:

$$w' = W_{max} \cdot \left(\frac{w}{W_{max}} + \lambda \left(1 - \frac{w}{W_{max}} \right)^{\mu+} \right) \cdot pre$$

$$w_{new} = \max(W_{max}, w')$$

where W_{max} is the maximum weight parameter, λ is weight change rate, $\mu+$ is the power law exponent (default 1), and pre is the pre-synaptic activations trace. The pre-synaptic activations trace is increased by 1 each time the pre-synaptic neuron fires, and decays with a time constant $\tau_{pre} = 20ms$.

Pre-synaptic depression works analogously, adding factor α in front of λ to account for asymmetry in the pre-/post-synaptic weight change factors.

Synaptic scaling

An unconstrained STDP plasticity can lead to unconstrained weight growth, which would induce a positive feedback loop and could increase modeled neurons connectivity indefinitely. It is not that pressing issue in the NEST STDP model, as growth there is limited by W_{max} - however, even there it leads to a steady state in weight changes. One common denomination of phenomena in living neuronal networks that have the ability to inhibit this infinite increase of connection strength between single coherently firing neuron pairs in a living cell culture is termed *synaptic scaling*. There are different rules and ways a living neuron can limit LTP activity, including maintaining a target firing rate throughout lifetime, releasing receptor inhibitors as a negative control feedback etc. [28] In my simulation, I employ *pre-synaptic scaling* rule: for each neuron i , the sum of its outgoing weights is preserved throughout the simulation. The main argument for the biological plausibility of this rule is that a single neuron has only as much matter and metabolites as to upkeep a pre-defined *physical volume* of synapses. Once a connection from i to another neuron j is made stronger, its physical volume increases. It hence attracts more matter and more metabolites, which come from other connections of i to different neurons than j . Then, the strengths of other connections necessarily decreases, because their volume decreases.

Practically, I calculate the sum $s_j(0) = \sum_i W_{ij}(0)$ of all outgoing connections from j at simulation time step 0, and the sum $s_j(t) = \sum_i W_{ij}(t)$ at time step t . Then, I update the weights (previously updated by STDP plasticity rule in the same timestep) as following:

$$\Delta W_{ij} = \frac{(s_j(0) - s_j(t))}{\tau_{SS} \cdot N_{conn}}$$

, where N_{conn} is the total number of existing outgoing connections of neuron j ($W_{ij} \neq 0$), and τ_{SS} is the time constant of synaptic scaling. I have determined τ_{SS} from previous simulations using a more straightforward and interpretable *synaptic scaling* rule:

$$W'_{ij} = W_{ij} \cdot \frac{s_j(0)}{s_j(t)}$$

, so at each time point the weights are being scaled by a ratio of the outgoing weight sum at time point 0 and time point t . I have then looked at how fast the weights decay under this rule, and fitted this decay to the exponential. The resulting denominator of exponential decay was $\tau_{SS} = 330ms$. I could transplace this time constant from one algorithm to another, because all steps but synaptic scaling were the same in both runs, and I have observed how synaptic scaling with factor multiplication affects weights when other rules were not active.

Synaptic depression

This plasticity rule is motivated by the finite amount of neurotransmitters that can be released into synaptic cleft by a neuron, as well as a distinct time it takes to replenish the neurotransmitter pool for subsequent firing. This limits neuron's ability to fire repeatedly in a short amount of time.

I model this as following (taken from [23]): initiate the dynamic vector D for each neuron i with $D_i = 1$ (which is interpreted as no synaptic depression, or the full amount of metabolites available). Each time a neuron fires, I update D_i as following:

$$D'_i = \beta \cdot D_i$$

, where β is a pre-defined parameter usually taken in range of 0.7 – 0.8 in my simulation runs. Each timestep t , D_i is being updated as following:

$$D(t+1) = \frac{1 - D(t)}{\tau_D}$$

D modifies the neuron output current. For timestep t the input current of each neuron is the uniform environmental noise discussed previously (let's denote it as η) plus the sum of all incoming connections multiplied by their synaptic depression factors. Put together as an equation

$$I_j^{inc}(t) = \eta_j(t) + \sum_i W_{ji} \cdot D_i(t)$$

That means that synaptic depression factors decrease the modelled strength of connection between neurons.

2.4 Results

In the core of this thesis, I have developed a simulation. One part of it is a state-of-the-art geometrically plausible network generation and connectivity initiation model [23]. The other part is a state-of-the-art neuronal activity model according to [26]. The novel part which I have added to the simulation are the selected synaptic plasticity mechanisms.

These were: spike-time dependent plasticity, synaptic scaling and synaptic depression. Either of the latter two, synaptic scaling and synaptic depression, can serve as a "growth brake" for spike-time dependent plasticity, which otherwise induces positive feedback loop on weight

Parameter	Explanation	Typical value (range)
N	Number of neurons	1000-3000
Pe	Fraction of excitatory neurons	0.8
r	Culture radius (mm)	0.1-1
ρ	Culture density ($\frac{\text{neurons}}{\text{mm}^2}$)	300-500
a	Izhikevich neuron's u factor	0.02 (exc.); $0.02 + 0.08U(0, 1)$ (inh.)
b	u nullcline factor	0.2 (exc.); $0.25 - 0.05U(0, 1)$ (inh.)
c	v reset value (mV)	$-65 + 15U(0, 1)^2$ (exc.); -65 (inh.)
d	δu on reset	$8 - 6U(0, 1)^2$ (exc.); 2 (inh.)
MAX_EXC_WEIGHT	Max. weight of exc. connections	5-10
MAX_INH_WEIGHT	Max. weight of inh. connections	0.1-1
β_{Hebb}	Increase in plasticity amplitude	0.02-0.2
τ_A	Plasticity amplitude decay rate (ms)	20
β_{depr}	Syn. depression amplitude change factor	0.7-0.8
τ_D	Syn. depression amplitude recovery rate (ms)	50
$\tau_S S$	Syn. scaling time constant (ms)	330
δt	Simulation time step (ms)	1

Table 2.1: Parameters of the simulation and their typical values

growth and produces exponentially growing weights.

Different plasticity mechanisms bring about tangible changes in simulation's process even on short runs. A way to show the detailed firing activity is shown on Figure 2.6. It is so called *raster plot* which is often used to visually inspect neuronal population firing. However, due to the fact that the culture fired so often (100-150ms inter-burst interval; Figure 2.7) these plots were not instructive. I utilized global activity plots. An example is shown on Figure 2.12: it is for the same time interval as the raster plot above. For better and smoother visualization I show a rolling average of spikes in 100ms sliding window using a Hamming taper.

Bursts across different plasticity mechanisms differed in how many neurons took part in them and how often they occurred, but also how fast they were from onset until dying out and how fast they propagated. No plasticity simulation bursts (Figure 2.9) stayed the same in global activity terms. Bursts of STDP simulation (Figure 2.10) constantly increased in size. Bursts of STDP + synaptic depression simulation are apparently growing slower in terms of global activity (Figure 2.11); this effect is even more pronounced in STDP + synaptic scaling simulation (Figure 2.13). Synaptic scaling apparently brings about relative stability of the globality of bursts, while synaptic depression seems to keep bursts in check in the short term, and then the global activity grows nevertheless. That being said, the simulation with 3 different mechanisms together is stabilized even more (Figure 2.14)

Analyzing inter-burst intervals using *find_peaks* function of *scipy* package, I have noticed that all the inter-burst interval distributions are significantly different.

I have also analyzed bursts of different synaptic plasticity rules using in-house *VISUALIZE_FRONTS* software of Prof. Dr. Jordi Soriano Fradera group. The most interesting metric was velocity of the calculated bursts propagation (Figure 2.8). Interestingly, STDP + synaptic depression bursts were propagating significantly faster on the average than STDP bursts. I would

Figure 2.6: Raster plot of the simulation with STDP and synaptic depression plasticity of 590-599s from simulation begin.

naively think the contrary, as STDP bursts should be more "aggressive" because they have no counteracting mechanisms. Maybe it is due to the fact that STDP bursts had few initiating neurons, which carry all others with them but require time for this. On the opposite, STDP + depression bursts have less "peaks" of the activity but for that run "smoother" and faster through the whole culture.

Overall, the simulation seemed to recapitulate well on the bursting behaviour observed in real neuronal cell cultures. Different plasticity rules provided variable global activity and inter-burst interval duration.

Figure 2.7: Inter-burst interval distribution for different synaptic plasticity mechanisms. All pairs are significant. Welch t-test was used for pair-wise comparison without multiple test correction.

Figure 2.8: Burst propagation velocity distribution. Welch t-test was used. Non-marked pairs are significant.

Figure 2.9: Bursts of the simulation with no plasticity.

Figure 2.10: Bursts of the simulation with STDP

Figure 2.11: Bursts of the simulation with STDP and synaptic depression.

Figure 2.12: Bursts of the simulation with STDP and synaptic depression in maximized view.

Figure 2.13: Rolling average of spikes/100ms with STDP and synaptic scaling.

Figure 2.14: Rolling average of spikes/100ms with STDP, synaptic depression and synaptic scaling.

3 Example of the model application: CNQX activity silencing experiment in a rat primary culture

To try and test the simulation capabilities on real data, I have applied it to simulate an experiment performed in Prof. Jordi Soriano Fradera's lab.

3.1 Experimental design

The idea of experiment was to evoke culture connectivity changes due to silencing of many of the culture's neuronal receptors. The main hypothesis is that neural culture tries to maintain the usual levels of activity, so upon silencing it would increase receptor number and/or strength. This would change connectivity strength between neurons. In particular, this would result in extra high activity of the culture once the silencing agents are washed off [29].

During the experiment, DIV 13 rat primary culture (Embryonic Stem Cells) were sprayed with different neurotransmitter blockers. Those were CNQX (blocks AMPA receptors), APV (blocks NDMA receptors) and biculline (blocks GABA receptors). Concentrations of BIC and APV were raised in one step to 20 μ M and 40 μ M respectively, and in the next steps the concentration of CNQX was gradually raised (in 3 steps: 300nM, 900nM, 15 μ M). A total of 4 steps of concentration increase for various synapse-blocking chemical agents were performed, and 10 minutes activity measurements using calcium imaging were recorded for each step (Figure 3.2). Although called "neurons" on the plot, the y-axis really depicts regions-of-interest in the culture.

After 72h (DIV 17) the culture's activity at the highest concentration of activity modifying chemicals was recorded again for 10 minutes, and then the chemicals were washed off completely. The culture's activity was then recorded immediately after, and 30 minutes, 4 hours and 24 hours after chemical agents' wash-off.

The important characteristic that we recorded for was thus the culture's firing activity. As we have seen from the Figure 3.2, culture fires less bursts than in the normal state with the highest concentration of chemicals added. After 4 days and the wash-off, the culture exhibits bursts that are less global (less neurons out of culture's neurons fire), but more frequent (Figure 3.3). 4 hours after wash-off, the spiking becomes less frequent, but for that more neurons fire in each burst.

The seen changes could happen because of several reasons. First, the fact that more neurons fire 4 hours after wash-off could be the sign of synchronization of synaptic depression between previously active and previously blocked neurons. However, there is no sign of

Figure 3.1: Raster plot of Calcium Imaging activity after spike sorting: DIV13, no chemicals added. Culture's "normal" firing state.

Figure 3.2: Raster plot of Calcium Imaging activity after spike sorting: DIV13, maximum concentrations of APV, BIC and CNQX. Excitatory synapses of the culture are silenced.

Figure 3.3: Raster plot of Calcium Imaging activity after spike sorting: DIV17, no APV, BIC and CNQX (30min post wash-off of these chemicals). Less neurons fire compared to normal state, but they burst much more often.

Figure 3.4: Raster plot of Calcium Imaging activity after spike sorting: DIV17, no APV, BIC and CNQX - 4 hours post wash-off of these chemicals. Almost the whole of the culture fires each burst, for that the interval between bursts is greater.

synaptic depression at 30 minutes after wash-off: the same neurons pertain the ability to fire frequently. Another aspect is the gradual regaining of function in the previously blocked channels. Whether due to some chemicals left, or slow metabolic pathways normalization, the gradually reestablished functioning could be the reason that less neurons fire in bursts at 30 minutes post-wash-off compared to 4 hours post-wash-off.

3.2 In-silico modelling of the silencing experiment

The expected connectivity modifications in the tested culture is clearly one of the aspects that my simulation could model. By employing the besaid plasticity rules (STDP, synaptic scaling and synaptic depression) that my colleagues and I picked in the previous step, I hoped to approximately account for culture changes during the chemicals addition and recuperation of culture's silenced connection by means of both structural and activity plasticity.

The addition of chemicals was modelled as global culture activity modifier γ , which decreases neuron's faculty to fire in the same way as synaptic depression does:

$$I_j^{inc}(t) = \eta(t) + \sum_i W_{ji} \cdot D_i(t) \cdot \gamma$$

On addition of chemicals, γ drops from 1 to 0.2 and held constant until it is washed off. The culture then fires with increased activity due to synaptic adaptation.

It also does not precisely model positions of *each single neuron in accordance with the experiment*, neither does it do so for the connections between neurons: it merely takes care about the correspondence of culture scale parameters to the parameter values observed experimentally, as well as it employs a geometrically plausible yet *randomized* axonal growth model. That renders most inquiries targeted at single-neuron precision comparison of the given simulation as compared to the experiment simply nonsensical, because any single neuron in the experiment would most probably not have the exact same correspondence in the simulation what concerns outgoing connections and placement on the surface.

3.3 Preparation of experiment simulation

As I had limited computational resources at hand, I had to proceed wisely and decide upon simulation details before the longer simulation run.

3.3.1 Metrics of activity correspondence

One of the most obvious metrics is the culture's global activity and bursting described in 1. Bursting extent and inter-bursting intervals is the metric that is more or less straightforward and lets tell how concordant or discordant real culture's and simulation's firing activities are. Another way is to perform a *dimensionality reduction* like PCA or similar and look at the *modular activity* of the network. Indeed, this is a way to subsume activity of multiple nodes and try and see if the model and the culture are similar in the reduced space.

Figure 3.5: Spikes of 2 hours MATLAB simulation with rolling average over 100ms Hemming taper. Important parts are marked with red lines and numbers. 1 - initial adjustments/transients, 2 - CNQX addition, 3 - recuperation of global activity, 4 - CNQX washoff, 5 - superlinear global activity increase, 6 - global activity decrease after steady increase.

3.4 Results of experiment simulation

In the end, I have chosen MATLAB as the simulation engine. I have used almost all of my quota at Leibniz-Rechenzentrum to run the simulation for 20 hours overnight. The results were *qualitatively* divergent in comparison to shorter simulations.

Figure 3.5 shows spiking activity of the 2 hour simulation using MATLAB using a rolling average. One can see how culture's activity increases in step 1. This corresponds to the adjustment/decaying transients of initial activity. In step 2, CNQX is being added to the culture. One can see the silenced activity by the drastically reduced burst neurons count. In step 3, culture seems to begin to "make up" for the suppressed activity by rearranging weights to bring the global activity up again. In step 4, CNQX is being *washed off* off the culture, which means weights are not reduced by factor γ anymore ($\gamma = 0.2$ in this experiment). In step 5, culture seems to steadily increase its global activity (beginning with a peculiar "kick-off" event just like this at the beginning of experiment). In step 6., after a steady super-linear increase culture's global activity seems to decrease. Interestingly, culture's global activity increases past the initial threshold in the "developed" culture, encompassing more than 800 out of 942 neurons in this experiment.

Analyzing the weights of the simulation, I have figured that their distribution was growing in both mean and variance (decreasing correspondingly for inhibitory weights). A look on

Figure 3.6: Weight distribution before CNQX addition, $t = 10\text{sec}$.

the distribution histograms, however, reveals a more interesting situation. The weights grow progressively from a nearly bi-uniform distribution (Figure 3.6) through addition of CNQX (Figure 3.7) to CNQX removal (Figure 3.8). However, there are only few "big scorers" who drive the whole distribution upwards. Interesting is also to point out that CNQX addition "nullified" many weights (ca. 25000 zero-weights at $t=2900\text{ sec}$.), some of which then increased again (ca. 20000 zero-weights at $t=5400\text{ sec}$.). This is hard to connect to the "big-scorers", as their magnitude continued to increase in this interval. Performing more simulations and drawing insights in this direction is certainly an interesting endeavour.

This simulation run results had apparent correspondence to the real culture. First, inter-burst intervals were getting gradually shorter before (Figure 3.9) to after (Figure 3.10) CNQX addition, and then even shorter after CNQX removal (Figure 3.11). Next, global activity of the culture after CNQX washoff was less than the maximum global activity of the culture before CNQX addition (in the normal state), but after some time it spiked even higher.

Using the in-house *VISUALIZE_FRONTS* software (Prof. Dr. Soriano Fradera group; not yet published), I have estimated bursts and computed burst estimation velocities from the simulation data and real data I had.

Figure 3.7: Weight distribution after CNQX addition + 1500 sec, t = 2900 sec.

Figure 3.8: Weight distribution after CNQX removal + 1000 sec, t = 5400 sec.

Figure 3.9: IBI distribution before CNQX addition.

Figure 3.10: IBI distribution after CNQX addition.

Figure 3.11: IBI distribution after CNQX removal.

Figure 3.12: Velocity of bursts in the CNQX experiment. 1-4: real data, 5-6: simulation.

As the timescale of bursts was mismatched between real experiment and the simulation, I have taken 5 minutes intervals from the real recording data and 10 second intervals from the simulation data, to reach 40-60 burst observations in each sample.

Figure 3.12 gives the overview of comparison. Real bursts velocity is hampered by CNQX on average, which would be expected from silencing the excitatory receptors in the culture. On day in vitro 18, the propagation velocity returns to a higher value.

I do not show the propagation velocities of the simulation for the time before the (simulated) CNQX addition, but those were in the range of 350mm/s. Interestingly, after the simulated CNQX addition, as well as the simulated CNQX washoff, propagation velocities in the simulated culture make a huge leap to be much closer to the ones observed in real cultures. There is, however, not any significant difference in the velocities after (simulated) CNQX addition and after (simulated) CNQX washoff in the real culture.

While the application to a real experiment demonstrated proximity of the constructed simulation to a real culture with regards to some metrics, it also has clearly shown some discrepancies that real culture's activity and the constructed simulation had.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

4.1 Conclusion

I have constructed a geometrically plausible simulation of real neuronal culture activity building upon a geometrically plausible algorithm of connection growth between neurons [23], a plausible and efficient neuronal activity model [26] with widely used synaptic plasticity mechanisms. I have applied the constructed simulation to a simple real experiment on a 2D neuronal network and highlighted the results.

4.1.1 Encountered difficulties

Differences of the simulation's model and the cell culture phenomenological reality

"Everything should be made as simple as possible, but not simpler" - Albert Einstein

The aim of the presented simulation is to make a "digital twin" of a real neuronal culture. My work builds upon the assumption that a set of three plasticity rules describes this connectivity changes in real neuronal culture with a sufficiently high accuracy. In reality, there is a myriad of processes involved in connectivity change, some of them far from synaptic plasticity alone: these processes range from synaptic metabolism changes that could lead to long-lasting phenomena such as LTP [30] to dynamical changes of organization on the macro-scale which could be linked to bursting activity of the culture [24]. I arguably could not implement them all at the same time keeping things efficient and interpretable - yet it is vital to understand that by the nature of my implementation, the simulation can be inaccurate. During this work, I have also viewed neurons as *stable entities* having stable properties describable by few simple parameters - which of course they are not. Changes are happening constantly in the transcriptome, proteome, and environmental milieu of these cells - which are hard to trace and hard to model. In my work, there is an implicit assumption that neurons do not substantially change in their firing properties throughout their lifetime, be it due to homeostasis or other properties. Only their *connectivity* does change. But does this term really explains what happens? Intercellular milieu between neurons can be as complicated as the cells themselves. The existence of perineuronal cell types like glia and astrocytes only makes it more complex. The used models are far from describing the whole complexity, dynamism and variety of the intercellular processes happening in real neuronal cultures.

Choice of plasticity rules

There are quite some hypotheses and publications about synaptic plasticity, as well as mathematical formulations of these changes [28]. How to choose which plasticity rules to include in the simulation?

The ones I used were presumably highly important for connectivity changes in real neurons, as well as efficiently computable, and last but not least the chosen combination avoided positive feedback loops, like those which the application of naive STDP could deliver [28]. There are many other plasticity rules that could be included., e.g. "metaplasticity" [31] or other types of synaptic scaling than weight sum homeostasis.

As showed in the thesis, leaving one of the "containing" rules out (synaptic scaling or synaptic depression) significantly changes the simulation result. One should proceed with care with adding or removing plasticity mechanisms from the simulation, even if they are seemingly similar and/or serve similar purpose. In the end, what is important is to model real culture's activity, and ideally the rules and only the rules delivering this should be implemented.

4.1.2 Differences of simulated vs. real activity

One of the apparent differences of the results mentioned above is the much higher spiking rate of a simulated culture as compared to the real one. This difference can be grounded in the parameters of the simulation, like spike delay time constants and weight increase magnitude and bounds. More research is needed to pinpoint and correct for the higher firing frequency of *in silico* culture.

Also the extent to which global activity of *in silico* model corresponds to the real culture's activity is unclear. While resembling real culture's activity *in vitro*, it still shows some specifics not precisely observed in experiments. This can be due to a poor precision of experiments: they are only recorded for a very limited time frame with gaps in-between, and Calcium imaging specifics (long time decay) does not allow to capture frequently fired spikes.

The simulation does not account for *real* network connections at the beginning of simulation. In other words, the edge conditions are brought in correspondence only based on *collective* culture metrics like neuron density, rough connection number estimate etc.

4.1.3 Culture geometry

Please note that this model does not account for other neuronal cell types than excitatory and inhibitory neurons (in particular, no astrocytes and microglia). Hence, it assumes that modelling excitatory and inhibitory neurons activity is enough to approximately predict the changes to these neurons' connectivity and firing.

It also does not precisely model positions of *each single* neuron *in accordance with the experiment*, neither does it do so for the connections between neurons: it merely takes care about the correspondence of culture scale parameters to the parameter values observed experimentally, as well as it employs a geometrically plausible yet *randomized* axonal growth model. That

renders most inquiries targeted at single-neuron precision comparison of the given simulation as compared to the experiment simply nonsensical, because any single neuron in the experiment would most probably not have the exact same correspondence in the simulation what concerns outgoing connections and placement on the surface.

4.1.4 Limitations of available real data

As mentioned before, the network in my simulation runs was defined only using the parameters of neuronal density and culture's diameter. Strictly speaking, in the available data we knew the position of neurons. It could have been unprecise: sometimes Calcium imaging has a too low resolution, which does not allow to detect a single neuron. Still, additional work could be done to include neuron soma positions in the algorithm of connection growth. Note that with the present Calcium imaging equipment and algorithm, it was not precisely possible to trace structural connections between neurons. However, it can be possible when using a superior equipment of better spatial resolution and imaging depth. This fact, too, can be incorporated in the initial network model.

Calcium imaging is also temporally unprecise due to a long decay. Low sample rate during recording results in a very ambiguous picture during the downstream analysis, illustrated e.g. by the Figure 4.1. Due to Calcium imaging specificities the burst is shown as almost simultaneous firing across culture. Even if there is a putative structure, there is no guarantee it is true because of the long fluorophore intensity decay.

The simulation operates on assumptions about neuronal biology and wiring made in [23], but in no part includes "real" connections between neurons - to a big extent, it is because we lack the data for that.

Therefore, we can not compare any single connection, far less their weights. Indeed, we can only take into account the *firing phenomena* happening in the real culture when looking at the simulation.

4.1.5 Performance considerations

There is yet another motivation to formulate connectivity change rules as simply as possible - to make it *compute*. A single additional plasticity rule can increase the runtime **by a factor** as shown in previous chapters, so one should be careful with choice and formulation of such changes.

I was not successful to bring the runtime-to-lifetime factor below 8x under circumstances. There are many factors to this: available computational resources, employed software packages and their parallelization capabilities. The developed simulation implementation can be further improved, which would allow it to run in a more time-efficient fashion and simulate for a longer lifetime. This allows space for new insights into real-world experiments. These experiments variety exceed the limits of an experiment described here in many aspects. Notably, the simulation can be improved to work with 3D cultures *in vitro* as well as stimulation experiments.

Figure 4.1: An example front - 16 from the DIV 17 + 4hr CNQX washoff computed with *VISUALIZE_FRONTS* software (Prof. Dr. Soriano Fradera). Low sample rate leaves the location of spiking and front structure ambiguous.

With many dynamically updated variables and matrix read-write operations, the projected operation and flops count of the described simulation are high. Most of experiments ran in the lab I was working with were under 30 days of colony growth, some other labs grow neuronal cultures/organoids for over a year for them to reach the level of mature activity variety [14]. As a rule of thumb, I aimed for the simulation to be ran in less than the time it models. So, for instance, the simulation of 1 second of colony's activity should be ran in less than 1 second computational time.

I have started modelling on my personal laptop with 4 GB RAM and AMD-A4 9125 2 CPU 2.3 GHz processor. It ran Windows and had a lot of software bugs. The results were terrible: I was a factor $\times 4$ slower on the simulation than the modelled time. It was apparent that simulation time grows linearly with increasing simulated time. The solution was not scalable. That led me to switch to an available Linux remote machine with 250 GB available RAM and Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2687W v3 @ 3.10GHz processor, and also without any apparent software bugs. With just the neuron activity simulation, I was able to get very good results: $\times 10$ faster simulation than the simulated lifetime. However, things started to become slower once I have started to implement plasticity mechanisms. The arguably most heavy plasticity mechanism is indeed the synaptic scaling - as it goes through the whole weight matrix W updating weights by the current change factors, which is an $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ hard operation. With all the plasticity mechanisms involved, simulation time grew drastically - becoming around factor 20x for the simulated time. It was not plausible in the long run, as even only under time linearity assumptions it would take 80 days to simulate 4 days of the colony lifetime. And that is not even taking into account space tracked data (spikes and other possible recorded data growing with time) would take.

4.1.6 Improving code performance

The big computational overhead of running the simulation was arguably due to inefficient places in the code among other things. Running MATLAB Profiler helped me to narrow down the issue: I have allocated space for arrays again and again in the loop, which took a big percentage of the total computational time of the program (Figure 4.2).

This was an issue amongst with other algorithmic considerations like updates that take more than $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ operations to perform (N being the number of neurons). Writing to array of spikes (which could grow in size with time) did not seem to be the issue in the small time setups (in fact, it is probably faster than writing to a file), so I did not modify the code in this regard.

With optimized array allocation (done not in the *for* loop, but beforehand), as well as substitution of *logical indexing* of array with matrix multiplication, it was possible to cut the runtime to 777sec for 50sec of culture's lifetime (Figure 4.3):

Still not sufficient.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

Figure 4.2: Profiler results for one of the revisions of the MATLAB simulation. Matrix space allocation takes up a considerable percentage of runtime.

Figure 4.3: Profiler results for 50 seconds of culture's lifetime. All possible optimizations to existing code reduce the runtime to factor 12x the simulated lifetime.

```

35 # main drive of spontaneous activity. Default is around 0.05
36 NOISE_MAX = 5.0;
37
38 T = 300000 | 300000
39 # MAIN SIMULATION
40 v = -65 * ones(Ne+Ni) # Initial values of v
41 u = b .* v # Initial values of u
42 rowsums_weights = sum(A, dims=1) # for homeostasis
43 neurontype_idx = [ones(Ne); -ones(Ni)]
44
45 spike_m = zeros(Ne+Ni, T)
46 ga = zeros(T)
47
48 colsums_weights_0 = sum(S, dims=1)
49 outgoing_conn_count = abs.(sum(A, dims=1));
50 not_connected = A .== 0;
51 firings = falses(Ne+Ni) # spike timings
52 I = zeros(Ne+Ni)

```

```

o bal variable
l @ ~/structfun/izhikevich_simulation.jl:79
; Warning: Assignment to `delta_w` in soft scope is ambiguous because a global variable by the same name exists: `delta_w` will be treated as a new local. Disambiguate by using `local delta_w` to suppress this warning or `global delta_w` to assign to the existing global variable.
l @ ~/structfun/izhikevich_simulation.jl:89
1557.506139 seconds (33.96 M allocations: 3.286 TiB, 1.94% gc time, 0.26% compilation time)
300000
o 5315.109635 seconds (80.48 M allocations: 9.737 TiB, 0.65% gc time, 0.00% compilation time)
julia>
julia>

```

Figure 4.4: Julia simulation results for 300s culture lifetime. The runtime is still about factor 20x the simulated lifetime.

4.1.7 Julia port of MATLAB code

Julia [32] is being advertised as a "fast dynamic language for technical computing", which is "easy to code as Python but runs as fast as C". I have used ChatGPT to convert MATLAB code to Julia faster [33]. After manual correction, I was able to test the code. It took 5315 seconds for 300 seconds lifetime simulation (Figure 4.4).

It was apparent that I either have to parallelize the code in some way, or go over to run even more low-level code. Parallelization would not be that straightforward, and could definitely not "resolve" the *for*-loop, as each time step in the simulation depends on the previous time steps. As I also did not want to lose time precision, I could not calculate multiple timesteps as one simulation step (increase δt). I have therefore decided to try one of the "leaders" in the market - NEST simulator - and see if I can make use of its C++ efficient simulation suite and in-built parallelization capabilities.

4.1.8 Using NEST for the simulation

NEST Simulator [34] is a versatile computational suite for simulating networks of many neurons. Its module NESTML provides a functionality to define custom neuron and synapse dynamics models. To get a first feeling of which runtime to expect from the suite, I have ran a network of 1000 Izhikevich neurons with STDP synapse model. I have left synaptic scaling and synaptic depression present in analysed MATLAB and Julia code for first to try

Figure 4.5: NEST Simulator distributes threads and virtual processes (VP_0) among the MPI processes P_0 and P_1 . 4 spike generators *sg*, 4 neurons *iaf* and 4 spike recorders *sr* are distributed on each virtual process.

and see whether this simple setup would have a sufficient runtime. I did not employ any parallelization at first; that is, OpenMP and MPI process counts were both at 1.

With the besaid definition (code is available in attachment), I have achieved a factor x2 runtime-to-lifetime. Already much better than the previous code runs - it seemed that in-built C++ compilation did a good work of optimizing the computations and reducing the overhead. Noteworthy, I have not yet recorded any spikes, nor have I added the noise - which, of course, also takes time and additional memory allocation.

Parallelization using NEST

Well, not that it was time for additional allocations: the computation still ran longer than the lifetime, even in this "succint" version. It was time to try out parallelization abilities that NEST had, because without a speed up computations made no sense.

NEST simulator uses Message Passing Interface (MPI) to distribute simulations onto multiple computing nodes [35], and OpenMP for multi-threading [36]. One of the benefits of NEST programs is the in-built parallelization of networks of many nodes - whereas in MATLAB I would have to parallelize nodes explicitly. An example of NEST parallelization is shown in Figure 4.5.

For the MPI parallelization side, I have used 8 nodes of provided 28-way Haswell-EP nodes with Infiniband FDR14 interconnect and 2 hardware threads per physical core, 56 GBytes per node. For the OpenMP threading, I have tried different combinations "blindly", because the program was reporting running with 1 OpenMP thread no matter that actual threads have actually been distributed in the OpenMP controller.

I have thought I could optimize endlessly, acquiring nodes and nodes for this purpose (the available cluster had 144). Well... not quite. First, the cluster was shared, so a fairshare policy was affecting the amount of hours I could spend on cluster. Second, the maximum amount of hours was set to around 96. Third, due to me updating weights outside of synapses the

available nodes count was restricted to 3 - at 4 nodes the program would hang due to the parallel I/O access to the node properties. With 2 nodes of 2 processes in their own turn 14 threads each, and collecting diagnostic output like synaptic weights and spike traces, I was able to achieve the runtime-to-lifetime factor of 8x. Still not great.

4.1.9 Parallelization of MATLAB program

In spite of long processing times no matter using NEST or MATLAB, I decided to try and come back to MATLAB and try parallelization there. The parallelization in MATLAB is pretty "stealthy" - meaning it does not get talked about "on the streets" (of World Wide Web) a lot, or it does but nobody knows about it. Nevertheless, it exists.

I have set up a buffer for the data, flushed spike and weight data in a file periodically, and ran a simulation on 1 node with 28 cores. And guess what - the runtime-to-lifetime factor was 10x! It was a small, but a victory. One can run MATLAB for the simulation, and it would not take much longer than NEST Simulator.

4.1.10 Implementation and runtime problems

MATLAB was banally inefficient, which I could actually improve a bit by running MATLAB in multi-threading mode on a machine with many cores. NEST seemed to be efficient at first, but was not at the end. This was due to additional nodes needed that produced Gaussian (white) noise, spike and weight recorders that took time to collect and write data. But most importantly, it was because of inability to use more than 3 nodes because of a parallelization bug; and in general, the unavailability of computing resources and parallel nodes to run the program on.

4.2 Outlook

This simulation, while apparently different in some of its aspects to the real culture, bears a resemblance of real culture's activity, thus providing a platform to investigate some of the real culture's properties *in silico*. This could save experimental costs, as well as shine light on the aspects of culture's activity overshadowed e.g. by noise in real experiments.

4.2.1 Refining the models

The simulation showed a much faster firing than the real culture. This could be controlled for by varying the modelled noise strength. Other parameters such as timescales of the plasticity rules can have significant impact on the resulting firing. It is possible that by tweaking it the simulation becomes closer to a "digital twin"

4.2.2 More and preciser data and experiments!

I did not have much data to test my assumptions on, and this could definitely be improved by doing more experiments. Only with sufficient real-world validation the presented simulation can be adjusted to reliably model it.

There are lots of neuro-recording methods: some are more efficient, some are cheaper. The used Calcium imaging lacked temporal, spatial and structural precision of firing activity. Neurons grew on a PDMS mould, the geometry of which can be varied. As has been shown by a fellow Master Thesis student of my supervisor, Mireia Olives Verger, as well as for example in [25], a richer spatial modular organization implies richer functional culture modularity. Ideally, one would have more information about the biological reality of involved cells - aquirable e.g. from automated Single-Molecule Light Microscopy [37] among other methods. This could be useful not only for firing activity, but for other confounders that could be included in the simulation to refine it.

4.2.3 3D cultures

There are ways to grow a 3D culture - not *plated* in 2D on any surface, and even assemble multiple 3D cultures into a so-called *assembloid* [38]. Compared with 2D, such cultures have the potential to reach a more complicated geometry, and hence more variative spiking activity. The downsides, however, lay in technical aspects of such cultures' growth and imaging. First, 3D cultures even more than 2D lack precise mechanisms of control for growth (number of cells, cell cycle etc.). This can be partially solved with the so-called growth factors - substances that guide the development of organoids through metabolic and regulatory pathways [39] [11]. Second, there is an acute need of blood vessels perfusion - without it cells inside of an organoid lack oxygen and risk dying out from it. There are methods which try to tackle this problem [40]. Third, with increasing size 3D cultures' activity becomes increasingly hard to record. Currently, the most advanced methods allow imaging only some 150 μ m inside the culture [37]. Bigger organoids' activity inside it can surely be inferred, but novel algorithms would be required for that.

4.2.4 Stimulation experiments

Electrical stimulation *per se* can be quite trivially included in the simulation - simply by modifying the input current vector to the targeted neurons at the needed time points. It is, however, more difficult to disentangle which neurons are being stimulated with which current precisely in the experiment, as electrical stimulation has its precision limits.

4.2.5 Criticality and network modularity increase

Criticality is the quality of a system which represents a state of transition between two stable states. For neuronal networks, critical state is optimal for message passing and represents the maximum dynamic range of neuronal communication [41]. Homogenous neuronal

cultures exhibit global, "all-at-once" bursting behaviour, which corresponds to supercritical dynamics and brains in pathological states. Subcritical dynamics are represented by the absence of bursting behaviour (random firing equal to noise). Meanwhile, critical behaviour is represented by partial bursting. In neuronal cultures, critical behavior can be achieved by topological patterning of neuronal cultures as the study of a fellow master student Mireia Olivia Verger shows. She proves that fractal PDMS patterning of cultures brings firing patterns in the culture to a critical state. The power law exponent of these firing patterns are close to the exponents observed in real "healthy" brains. This means it might be profitable to care about appropriate topological patterning and module induction in real neuronal cultures experiments to make them a better model of real brains and endow them with superior information processing capabilities.

4.2.6 Possible experiments and implications of cell culture research

One of the most interesting directions concerning 3D cultures and/or organoid is to apply targeted stimulation of their activity. Would it cause significant changes in its biology, in its activity patterns? One of the most difficult research questions in neuronal cell cultures is their maturation. Reasoning from that real brains mature by receiving sensory experience, which essentially goes through electrical stimuli in the brain, one could try and apply direct electrical stimulation to the neurons inside a *dish* to try and make the culture more mature.

If one draws a parallel between a neuronal cell culture and a real brain, would it have the ability to process the input in a meaningful way? To store a "memory" of it? To "learn"?

There are bold papers and initiatives claiming that organoids can possess intelligence and act like intelligent agents [42]. Recently, the whole frontier of Organoid Intelligence has been called to life. It has additionally been proclaimed one of the priority research directions in the United States [43]. An Australian startup CorticalLabs works on a so-called DishBrain™ to offer as an Artificial Intelligence as a Service to customers in Q4 2023. CorticalLabs has already produced a scientific study elaborating on the culture's ability to learn the game of pong [44]. The coming years will show the real potential of organoids and neuronal cultures to acquire intelligence.

From my perspective and my learnings during the writing of this Master Thesis, it is yet a far way to go until we can reach a reliable apparatus of intelligence in form of neuronal cell cultures. From the biological point of view, how do we make the development and maturation process of organoids more controllable and fail-safe, as well as their lifetime less damaging and/or pathological? From the recording point of view, how do we come to have a better precision and recording depth investigating organoids' metabolic processes? From the modelling point of view, how to come up with better mathematical description of underlying biological processes? From the point of view of cognition, how do we interpret the processes inside the organoid, the way it processes the signals and changes its state, and what terms do we use for that (assuming we wouldn't just equate it to human "cognition")? These questions should be answered before a significant and scaleable technological leap in the direction of Organoid Intelligence can be achieved.

Most organoids nowadays are small and "childish" - that is, they do not grow bigger than few

millimeters and their development stage is usually days close to embryonic undifferentiated stem cell. Mature organoids are known to develop a richer neuronal activity repertoire, but it is hard to grow an organoid to reach this stage avoiding significant cell loss [14]. Even in the limited setting of quasi-homogenous neuronal tissue of small size, neuronal cell colonies show interesting and rich functional organisation and sophisticated spontaneous activity patterns. A good model of neuronal cell culture activity would allow for better *in silico* understanding of colony's working principles, its "neural code", and would also allow to investigate different perturbations to the colony before trying it in the dish.

4.2.7 Ethics of neuronal cell culture and Organoid research

Exactly because of the processes in brain organoids could become so advanced in their complexity and information capabilities that they could be called "conscious", there are a lot of ethical questions created by that. Can we speak of organoids as intelligent and *sentient* agents? If so, is it morally permissible to perform clinical research and experiments on them [45]? This and many other questions which are outside of the scope of this work exist in the area of Ethics of neuronal cell cultures and organoids. Every stakeholder in this research should ideally be aware of increasing importance of these questions for the whole of society with the increasing success of neuronal cell culture applications.

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Acronyms

AMPA -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic. 25

APV (2R)-amino-5-phosphonopentanoate. 25, 27–29, 52

BIC Biculline. 25, 27–29, 52

CNQX Cyanquixaline. v, 25–38, 52

DIV Days in vitro. 25–29, 52

EEG Electroencephalogram. 1

GABA 4-aminobutanoic acid. 25

in silico In a computer (lat.). 50

in vitro In a probe glass (lat.). 3, 6

in vivo In a living organism (lat.). 3

iPSC Induced pluripotent stem cells. 1

LTP Long-term potentiation. 39

NDMA N-Nitrosodimethylamine. 25

PDMS Polydimethylsiloxane. 48

STDP Spike time-dependent plasticity. 12, 20–24, 51, 52

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